

Identification of Erbium(III) Chloride Solvate $\text{ErCl}_3(\text{thf})_{3.5}$: Crystal and Molecular Structure of the Ion-pair $[\text{trans-ErCl}_2(\text{thf})_5][\text{trans-ErCl}_4(\text{thf})_2]$

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Manuscript received 12 December 1997, accepted 23 February 1998

$\text{ErCl}_3(\text{thf})_{3.5}$ has been identified by an X-ray diffraction study as the ionic salt $[\text{trans-ErCl}_2(\text{thf})_5][\text{trans-ErCl}_4(\text{thf})_2]$. The monocation features a seven-coordinate erbium atom with a *trans*- ErCl_2 unit (Er-Cl, 2.563(2) Å) surrounded by five tetrahydrofuran molecules (Er-O, in the range 2.383(8)–2.393(8) Å) in a regular pentagonal bipyramidal geometry. The anion is six-coordinate with an octahedral metal geometry comprising four equatorial chlorine atoms (Er-Cl, 2.593(3) and 2.609(3) Å) and two axial tetrahydrofuran molecules (Er-O, 2.313(9) Å).

Lanthanide chloride tetrahydrofuran solvates $\text{LnCl}_3(\text{thf})_x$ are not restricted to one particular stoichiometry, rather $|x|$ may take values 2, 3, 3.5 or 4 and structurally characterised examples for each of these have been reported, e.g., $\text{CeCl}_3(\text{thf})_2^1$, $\text{LuCl}_3(\text{thf})_3^2$, $\text{DyCl}_3(\text{thf})_{3.5}^3$ and $\text{NdCl}_3(\text{thf})_4^4$. Those adducts featuring a $\text{LnCl}_3(\text{thf})_{3.5}$ stoichiometry are perhaps the most challenging in terms of structural recognition since a mononuclear adduct is clearly not a possibility. There are three examples (Ln = Tb¹, Dy³ and Y⁵) and X-ray structure determinations reveal penta-solvated cations LnCl_2^+ and di-solvated anions LnCl_4^- as an ion-pair arising from auto-ionisation in solution. Examples of lanthanide $[\text{LnX}_2(\text{thf})_5]^+$ cations derived from non-auto-ionised systems include $[\text{SmI}_2(\text{thf})_5][\text{Co}(\text{CO})_4]^6$ and $[\text{YCl}(\text{OCMe}_3)(\text{thf})_5][\text{BPh}_4]^7$ together with the related $[\text{SmI}_2(\text{Ph}_2\text{MeP}=\text{O})_5]^8$. The underlying reasons for the startling structural variety of $\text{LnCl}_3(\text{thf})_n$, as obtained from what is *prima facie* a simple metal halide ~ solvent system, have been discussed previously⁹ in terms of size variations between lanthanide ions. For Ln = Er our prediction of the $n = 3.5$ classification involving auto-ionisation is now shown to be correct. Herein we describe the formation and crystal structure determination of $[\text{trans-ErCl}_2(\text{thf})_5][\text{trans-ErCl}_4(\text{thf})_2]$.

Results and Discussion

Pink crystals of $\text{ErCl}_3(\text{thf})_{3.5}$ (**1**) were obtained by slow cooling of a hot saturated solution of anhydrous ErCl_3 in tetrahydrofuran. These proved to be extremely moisture-sensitive, degrading rapidly in contact with air. The infrared spectrum contains bands at 1019 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COC})$ and 852 cm^{-1} $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COC})$, characteristic of coordinated tetrahydrofuran with a broad intense band at 262 cm^{-1} arising from $\nu(\text{ErCl})$.

Crystal data are given in Table 1, together with refinement details. An X-ray diffraction study revealed the structure of **1** as a cation-anion pair consisting of discrete

TABLE 1—CRYSTAL DATA AND STRUCTURE REFINEMENT

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{56}\text{Cl}_6\text{Er}_2\text{O}_7$
Formula weight	1051.95
Temperature	180 (2) K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$C2/c$
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 12.447$ (6) Å $\alpha = 90^\circ$ $b = 11.383$ (6) Å $\beta = 91.328$ (13) $^\circ$ $c = 27.372$ (13) Å $\gamma = 90^\circ$
Volume, Z	3877 (3) Å ³ , 4
Density (calculated)	1.802 Mg m ⁻³
Absorption coefficient	4.751 mm ⁻¹
$F(000)$	2072
Crystal size	0.22 × 0.20 × 0.18 mm
θ range for data collection	1.49 to 25.00 $^\circ$
Limiting indices	$-16 \leq h \leq 14$, $-11 \leq k \leq 15$, $-36 \leq l \leq 28$
Reflections collected	9676
Independent reflections	3379 ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0677$)
Max. and min. transmission	0.5045 and 0.5930
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Data/restraints/parameters	3379/40/215
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	0.991
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R1 = 0.0673$, $wR2 = 0.1810$ (for 2449 reflections)
R indices (all data)	$R1 = 0.0867$, $wR2 = 0.1901$
Largest diff. peak and hole	6.396 and -1.666 eÅ ⁻³

$[\text{ErCl}_2(\text{thf})_5]^+$ cations and $[\text{ErCl}_4(\text{thf})_2]^-$ anions. Table 2 contains a list of selected bond lengths and angles. The cation (Fig. 1 with atom notation) is seven-coordinate with a linear Cl-Er-Cl unit (179.6(2) $^\circ$), and a pentagonal girdle of tetrahydrofuran molecules. The Er-Cl bond distances 2.563(3) and 2.562(3) Å compare favourably with those in the cation $[\text{ErCl}_2(12\text{-crown-4})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+^{10}$ Er-Cl 2.590(3), 2.674(3) Å and the related $\text{CpErCl}_2(\text{thf})_3^{11}$ Er-Cl 2.613(1), 2.620(1) Å and $[\text{ErCl}_3(\text{triethyleneglycol})].\text{MeOH}^{12}$ Er-Cl

TABLE 2—SELECTED BOND LENGTHS Å AND ANGLES (°)

Er(1)—O(1)	2.385(12)	Er(1)—O(3)	2.383(8)
Er(1)—O(3) ^{#1}	2.383(8)	Er(1)—O(2) ^{#1}	2.393(8)
Er(1)—O(2)	2.393(8)	Er(1)—Cl(11) ^{#1}	2.562(3)
Er(1)—Cl(11)	2.563(3)	Er(2)—O(4)	2.313(9)
Er(2)—O(4) ^{#2}	2.313(9)	Er(2)—Cl(21) ^{#2}	2.593(3)
Er(2)—Cl(21)	2.593(3)	Er(2)—Cl(22) ^{#2}	2.609(3)
Er(2)—Cl(22)	2.609(3)		
O(1)—Er(1)—O(3)	144.0(2)	O(1)—Er(1)—O(3) ^{#1}	144.0(2)
O(3)—Er(1)—O(3) ^{#1}	72.0(4)	O(1)—Er(1)—O(2) ^{#1}	72.1(2)
O(3)—Er(1)—O(2) ^{#1}	142.9(3)	O(3) ^{#1} —Er(1)—O(2) ^{#1}	72.5(3)
O(1)—Er(1)—O(2)	72.1(2)	O(3)—Er(1)—O(2)	72.5(3)
O(3) ^{#1} —Er(1)—O(2)	142.9(3)	O(2) ^{#1} —Er(1)—O(2)	144.3(5)
O(1)—Er(1)—Cl(11) ^{#1}	89.82(8)	O(3)—Er(1)—Cl(11) ^{#1}	86.2(2)
O(3) ^{#1} —Er(1)—Cl(11) ^{#1}	94.1(2)	O(2) ^{#1} —Er(1)—Cl(11) ^{#1}	86.1(2)
O(2)—Er(1)—Cl(11) ^{#1}	93.8(2)	O(1)—Er(1)—Cl(11)	89.82(8)
O(3)—Er(1)—Cl(11)	94.1(2)	O(3) ^{#1} —Er(1)—Cl(11)	86.2(2)
O(2) ^{#1} —Er(1)—Cl(11)	93.8(2)	O(2)—Er(1)—Cl(11)	86.1(2)
Cl(11) ^{#1} —Er(1)—Cl(11)	179.6(2)	O(4)—Er(2)—O(4) ^{#2}	180.0
O(4)—Er(2)—Cl(21) ^{#2}	89.9(2)	O(4) ^{#2} —Er(2)—Cl(21) ^{#2}	90.1(2)
O(4)—Er(2)—Cl(21)	90.1(2)	O(4) ^{#2} —Er(2)—Cl(21)	89.9(2)
Cl(21) ^{#2} —Er(2)—Cl(21)	180.0	O(4)—Er(2)—Cl(22) ^{#2}	89.0(2)
O(4) ^{#2} —Er(2)—Cl(22) ^{#2}	91.0(2)	Cl(21) ^{#2} —Er(2)—Cl(22) ^{#2}	91.69(11)
Cl(21)—Er(2)—Cl(22) ^{#2}	88.31(11)	O(4)—Er(2)—Cl(22)	91.0(2)
O(4) ^{#2} —Er(2)—Cl(22)	89.0(2)	Cl(21) ^{#2} —Er(2)—Cl(22)	88.31(11)
Cl(21)—Er(2)—Cl(22)	91.69(11)	Cl(22) ^{#2} —Er(2)—Cl(22)	180.0

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms :

#1 $-x, y, -z+1/2$. #2 $-x+1, -y+3/2, -z$

2.565(2), 2.589(2) and 2.615(2) Å. The Er-O_{thf} bond distances are in the range 2.383(8)–2.393(8) Å, c.a., CpErCl₂(thf)₃¹¹ Er-O_{thf} 2.350(3)–2.452(3) Å. The cation structure is almost 'ideal' in that all five O–Er–O angles lie within the narrow range 72.0(4)–72.5(3)° and the ten O–Er–Cl angles are between 86.1(2) and 94.1(2)° although several of the tetrahydrofuran molecules do show some degree of disorder, as can be seen from Fig. 1.

The six-coordinate anion (Fig. 2 with atom notation) is centrosymmetric with four chlorine atoms (equatorial) and two tetrahydrofuran molecules mutually *trans* with Er-O_{thf} 2.313(9) Å and O–Er–O 180° by crystal symmetry. The unique Er–Cl bond lengths 2.593(3) and 2.609(3) Å, are perceptibly longer than those of the cation and, as expected, this trend is observed in previous LnCl₃(thf)_{3,5} examples : Ln = Dy³, cation 2.624(5), anion 2.641(5), 2.644(5) Å, Ln = Tb³, cation 2.598(1), anion 2.637(1), 2.621(1) Å; and Ln = Y³, cation 2.555(3), anion 2.599(3), 2.588(3) Å. This presumably reflects the negative charge on the metal repelling the chloride ions to a greater extent than any contrac-

tion due to less steric congestion with the lower coordination number.

Fig. 1. Structure of the [ErCl₂(thf)₅]⁺ cation.

Fig. 2. Structure of the $[\text{ErCl}_4(\text{thf})_2]^-$ anion.

On the basis that holmium lies between dysprosium and erbium in the lanthanide series, we anticipate that the $\text{HoCl}_3\text{-thf}$ system currently under investigation will similarly provide an auto-ionised adduct to join the $x = 3.5$ solvate classification.

Experimental

Manipulations were carried out using standard Schlenk techniques in conjunction with a dinitrogen filled glove-box. Tetrahydrofuran was pre-dried over CaH_2 and then freshly distilled from potassium prior to use. Anhydrous erbium(III) chloride (Aldrich) was used without further purification. Ir spectra were recorded as nujol mulls between CsI plates using a Perkin-Elmer 580B instrument, and elemental analyses were carried out using a Leeman Lab Inc., CE440 elemental analyser.

Preparation of $\text{ErCl}_3(\text{thf})_{3.5}$: Erbium(III) chloride (1.51 g, 5.52 mmol) was added to tetrahydrofuran (50 cm^3) and the resulting mixture was stirred at 60° for 2 h. The resulting solution was filtered and the filtrate allowed to cool gradually to room temperature. The pink cubic crystals which deposited were washed with n-hexane (3 $\times$ 30 cm^3) and allowed to dry in a nitrogen atmosphere (1.76 g, 61%), (Found : C, 31.87; H, 5.31; Cl, 20.34; Er, 32.08. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_6\text{Er}_2$ calcd. for : C, 31.97; H, 5.37; Cl, 20.22; Er, 31.80%); $\bar{\nu}_{\text{max}}$ (nujol) 1304m, 1169m, 1019s $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COC})$, 917m, 852s $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COC})$, 770w, 664w, 498w (ligand), 262 s $\text{br cm}^{-1} \nu(\text{ErCl})$.

X-Ray crystallography: Crystal data were collected using a Siemens SMART CCD area-detector diffractometer. A full hemisphere of reciprocal space was scanned by a combination of three sets of exposures; each set had a dif-

ferent ϕ angle for the crystal and each exposure of 10 s covered 0.3° in ω . The crystal to detector distance was 5.01 cm. Crystal decay was monitored by repeating the initial frames at the end of the data collection and analyzing the duplicate reflections, and was found to be negligible. A multi-scan absorption correction was applied using SADABS¹³.

The structure was solved by direct methods using SHELXTL-PC¹⁴ and refined by full matrix least-squares on F^2 for all data using SHELXL-97¹⁵. Hydrogen atoms were added at calculated positions and refined using a riding model. Anisotropic temperature factors were used for all non-H atoms; H-atoms were given isotropic displacement parameters equal to 1.2 times the equivalent isotropic displacement parameter of the atom to which the H-atom is attached. Crystal quality was poor and some twinning was apparent from an examination of the diffraction intensity profiles. Two large spurious peaks of residual electron density may be attributed to the crystal twinning.

Additional material available either from the Cambridge Crystallographic Database Centre or the authors comprises hydrogen atom coordinates, thermal parameters and a complete set of bond distances and angles.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the University of Warwick for a post-graduate scholarship to one of them (T.J.W.) and, together with Siemens plc and the EPSRC, for funding of the X-ray facilities.

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